

Wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ From Free and Infinite Well Comparisons?

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It is well-known that within an infinite well there is no potential so solutions to the Schrodinger equation $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are identical to solutions in free space. These two are added to create $C_1 \sin(px)$ if the box extends from 0 to L with $p = n\pi/L$ so that the wavefunction is 0 outside of the box. If one considers all of space as in (1) then $W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. Thus p in $\sin(px)$ is called p (average) and it is stressed that all p 's combine to create the particle in an infinite well. Although this is true, we wish to stress that the wavefunction $\sin(px)$ has no variance of powers of p if one defines variance as: $\int dp P(p/x) (p - \text{pave})^n$ where $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / C_1 \sin(px)$. For example average p is pave etc.

In this note, we assume a function $f(p,x)$ as describing a special probability distribution (a dynamic one which may have positive and negative values and may even be complex) for a free particle. We assume that within an infinite well one has a combination of $f(\text{pave},x)$ and $f(-\text{pave},x)$ and no variance p 's. We investigate whether this leads to the form $\exp(ipx)$.

Alternate Arguments for $\exp(ipx)$

In a previous note (2) we argued that the relativistic or nonrelativistic action $A = -m_0 t \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ or $A = m_0 t \cdot \frac{1}{2} v^2$ could be written with $v = x/t$ and x and t varied independently to yield:

$$dA/dx \text{ partial} = p \text{ and } dA/dt = -E \text{ so } A = -Et + px \quad ((1))$$

If one wishes to create an eigenvalue equation then one has:

$$-i \hbar / dx \text{ partial} \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA) \text{ and } i \hbar / dt \text{ partial} \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA) \quad ((2))$$

This still begs the question: Why should one want an eigenvalue equation?

Another argument is that a particle performs a kind of rotation in two dimensional space (i.e. complex number) as it moves. Thus one has $f(p,x) + i g(p,x)$ with f and g being periodic functions. If one wishes this description to represent a kind of dynamic probability while at the same time preserving invariance of x (i.e. a momentum impulse of p may be delivered by the particle at any x) one may suggest:

$$[f(p,x) - i g(p,x)] [f(p,x) + i g(p,x)] = 1 \quad ((3)) \text{ A solution is } f(p,x) = \cos(px) \text{ and } g(p,x) = \sin(px)$$

In this note, we investigate if one may obtain the form $\exp(ipx)$ by comparing a free particle dynamic probability (wavefunction) with that of a particle in a box with infinite potential walls.

Free Particle and Particle in an Infinite Well

In quantum mechanics it is known that the time-independent Schrodinger equation within an infinite well yields free particle solutions $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ in this region. Outside the well which exists from 0 to L the wavefunction is zero. Thus if $\exp(ipx)$ is the wavefunction of a free particle it is stressed in (1) that actually all p values are needed to create an $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ within the well.

A main point we wish to stress is that although all p values are used, the wavefunction within the box, (i.e. a kind of dynamic probability) creates no variances. For example if one has $\exp(ipx)$ then the average of p within the box is $\int_0^L p \exp(ipx) dx / \int_0^L \exp(ipx) dx$ just as for a free particle with a momentum of $\hbar k$ etc. One may create the variance of energy at each point $(\hbar^2 k^2 / 2m - E)(\hbar^2 k^2 / 2m - E)$ and this is also 0 at each x point. This is not the case for other systems such as a quantum oscillator.

As a result, for the particle in an infinite well one has within 0 to L one has the sum of $f(p,x)$ and $f(-p,x)$ which we call $g(p,x)$. Then at x

$$\int dp a(p) f(p,x) = g(pave, x) \quad x \text{ in } (0,L) \quad ((4a))$$

$$\int p^n a(p) f(p,x) = pave^n g(pave, x) \quad x \text{ in } (0,L) \quad ((4b))$$

Note $g(pave,x)$ on the RHS is really a normalization function at x which has been brought over from the LHS. For all other systems $f(pave, x)$ would be $W_n(x)$. It is for the comparison of a particle in an infinite well with a free particle that one has $f(p,x)$ on the RHS and $g(pave, x)$ on the left. (Note the close connection between $f(p,x)$ and $g(p,x)$ i.e $g(p,x) = c[f(p,x)+f(-p,x)]$

$$((4)) \text{ suggests that: } \int dp a(p) f(p,x) = \int \delta(p-pave) g(p,x) \quad ((5))$$

As a result, ((4b)) could be satisfied if there existed an x dependent operator which could produce powers of p. If so it would act on $f(p,x)$ which would be of the form $f(px)$. In such a case

$f(px) = \exp(ipx)$ with the operator being $-i\hbar/dx$ is a solution. In such a scenario an eigenvalue equation for p makes sense i.e. $-i\hbar/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$.

Thus we argue that comparing a free particle $f(px)$ with a particle in an infinite well suggests that $f(px)=\exp(ipx)$ and $-i\hbar/dx$ be a momentum operator. This has the added benefit of having a modulus of 1 which we argue indicates that the particle may impart an impulse of p at any x.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that although a particle in an infinite well requires a superposition of all free particle wavefunctions (1) in order to create a free particle type solution within the well and

a zero wavefunction outside and that $\langle p \rangle$ applies to the solution inside, we argue there is no variance for p . In other words one has $\langle p \rangle$, the average of p is $\langle p \rangle$ etc. Using this we write expressions for the average of p^n and note that if $f(p,x)$ the free particle wavefunction is of the form $\exp(ipx)$ one may satisfy these expressions. We argue that this may be an approach to establishing $\exp(ipx)$ as the free particle wavefunction.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Particle_in_a_box
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Lagrangian/Action Formalism as a Flow Scheme? (preprint, zenodo, 2021)